

SPRING WATERS IN GALLAOROL (SPRING NO. 19 AND SPRING NO. 20)

Tashpulatova Sabokhat Akbarovna¹

(PhD student)

Makhkamova Malika Akhror qizi²

(Bachelor degree student)

Khodiyeva Aziza Dilshod qizi³

(Bachelor degree student)

Kamiljanova Shakhrizoda Akbarovna⁴

(Bachelor degree student)

¹⁻²⁻³⁻⁴National University of Uzbekistan, Ecology Faculty, Uzbekistan

Tel: +99893 299 25 42

E-mail: sabo_8728@mail.ru

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Abstract: Gallaorol district, which is part of the mountainous region of Jizzakh region, is famous for its many springs. The results of chemical laboratory analysis of the samples taken from these springs are described in the study. Physical and chemical indicators of water are in accordance with state standards for water quality.

Key words: Physico-chemical analysis, Spring No. 19, Spring No. 20, State standards, water quality standard, human health.

INTRODUCTION

Water is an integral, important part of human life. Water quality is a very important factor in the normal functioning of physiological processes in the human body. Water has played an important role in the formation of human civilization since time immemorial. Groundwater is a fresh water reservoir, and springs are a "product" of groundwater. Jizzakh region is an important mountainous region of Uzbekistan, and it plays a unique role in agriculture, industry and production. Gallaorol district is one of the mountainous districts of Jizzakh region, and most of the population of the region lives in this region. Most of the population of Gallaorol lives in villages. The main source of water for the villagers is the underground natural spring water sources that are widespread throughout the region. Springs are not only the main source of consumption of the villagers, but also the only source for use for economic and household purposes, as well as for gardening and homestead purposes.

In-depth study of the chemical composition of spring waters plays a key role in their rational use. Below are the results of chemical laboratory analysis of samples taken from these spring water. The results of this chemical analysis were compared with the national water quality standards.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The springs in the Gallaorol region were conditionally named with numbers (Spring No. 19, Spring No. 20). Water samples from spring waters were placed in 1.5 liter polyethylene bottles, and their chemical analyzes was determined by a chemical analytical laboratory method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Spring No.19, Spring No. 20 in Gallaorol district of Jizzakh region was studied. The results of the chemical analysis of the samples taken from these spring water are analyzed. The pH indicator of Spring No. 19 is 7, 2, which corresponds to the state standards of Uzbekistan (requirements for the quality of domestic and drinking water - 6.00-9.00), and it is neutral. The SiO_2 indicator of spring water is 1.5 mg/dm^3 , and the indicator is suitable in the state standards. The dry residue of spring water is 400.3 mg/dm^3 , and the state standards state that it should be $1000.0\text{-}1500.00 \text{ mg/dm}^3$, which means that it also meets the requirements for this indicator. The amount of Ca^{2+} from cations is 62.1 mg/dm^3 , the amount of Mg^{2+} is 30.4 mg/dm^3 , Fe - $<0.05 \text{ mg/dm}^3$, and meets state standards (0.3). From anions, CO_3^{2-} - $<5, 0 \text{ mg/dm}^3$, HCO_3^- - 176.9, SO_4^{2-} - 120.0 (400.00-500.00 by standard), Cl - 14.18 (250.00-350.00 by standard), NO_2^- - 0.01, NO_3^- - 13.0 mg/dm^3 conforms to state standards (45.00). The total hardness of spring water is $5.6 \text{ mg-equiv/dm}^3$, which suitable the standard requirements (7.00-10.00).

The pH indicator of Spring No. 20 is 7, 6, which corresponds to the state standards of Uzbekistan (requirements for the quality of domestic and drinking water - 6.00-9.00), and it is weak alkaline. The SiO_2 indicator of spring water is 2.3 mg/dm^3 , and the indicator is suitable in the state standards. The dry residue of spring water is 410.1 mg/dm^3 , and the state standards state that it should be $1000.0\text{-}1500.00 \text{ mg/dm}^3$, which means that it also meets the requirements for this indicator. The amount of Ca^{2+} from cations is 70.1 mg/dm^3 , the amount of Mg^{2+} is 20.7 mg/dm^3 , Fe - 0.24 mg/dm^3 , and meets state standards (0.3). From anions, CO_3^{2-} - $<5, 0 \text{ mg/dm}^3$, HCO_3^- - 231.8, SO_4^{2-} - 69.2 (400.00-500.00 by standard), Cl - 49.6, (250.00-350.00 by standard), NO_2^- - 0.01, NO_3^- - 17.3 mg/dm^3 conforms to state standards (45.00). The total hardness of spring water is $5.2 \text{ mg-equiv/dm}^3$, which suitable the standard requirements (7.00-10.00).

A comparison of the results of chemical analysis of these two springs can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1.

Chemical analyze results of Spring No. 19 and Spring No. 20 (mg/dm^3)

Spring name	pH	SiO ₂ mg/dm ³	Dry residue mg/dm ³	Ca ⁺ mg/dm ³	Mg ⁺ mg/dm ³	Fe mg/dm ³	CO ₃ ²⁻ mg/dm ³	HCO ₃ ⁻ mg/dm ³
Spring No. 19	7.2	1.5	400.3	62.1	30.4	< 0.05	<5.0	176.9
Spring No. 20	7.6	2.3	410.1	70.1	20.7	0.24	<5.0	231.8
State standards of Uzbekistan (UzDSt 951:2011)	6.00-9.00	---	1000.00-1500.00	---	---	0.3	---	---
State Standard of Uzbekistan (UzDSt 0950:201)	6.00-9.00	---	1000.00-1500.00	---	---	0.3	---	---

Spring name	SO ₄ ²⁻ mg/dm ³	Cl ⁻ mg/dm ³	NO ₂ ⁻ mg/dm ³	NO ₃ ⁻ mg/dm ³	Total hardness mg-equiv/dm ³
Spring No. 19	120.0	7.09	0.01	25.8	3.9
Spring No. 20	69.2	49.6	0.01	17.3	5.2
State standards of Uzbekistan (UzDSt 951:2011)	400.00-500.00	250.00-350.00	---	45.00	7.00-10.00
State Standard of Uzbekistan (UzDSt 0950:2011)	400.00-500.00	250.00-350.00	---	45.00	7.00-10.00

The amount of K, Na, Mn, Pb, Cu, Cr, Zn, Ni, Co, As, CNS, Al was determined in the water of Spring No. 19 and Spring No. 20 (Table 2).

Table 2.

Chemical analysis results of Spring No. 19 and Spring No. 20 (mg/dm³)

Chemical analysis results of Spring No. 19

No.	Chemical element	mg/dm ³	No.	Chemical element	mg/dm ³
1	K	1,4	7	Zn	0,03
2	Na	23,9	8	Ni	0,09
3	Mn	<0,05	9	Co	0,31
4	Pb	<0,02	10	As	0,1
5	Cu	0,02	11	CNS	9,7
6	Cr	0,05	12	Al	<10,0

Chemical analysis results of Spring No. 20

No.	Chemical element	mg/dm ³	No.	Chemical element	mg/dm ³
1	K	11,6	7	Zn	0,03
2	Na	34,3	8	Ni	0,1
3	Mn	<0,05	9	Co	0,30
4	Pb	<0,02	10	As	0,1
5	Cu	0,02	11	CNS	9,7
6	Cr	0,05	12	Al	<10,0

Chemical analysis results (Table 2) Hygienic requirements and quality control for the supply of domestic drinking water to the state standards of Uzbekistan (UzDSt 951:2011) fully comply with the requirements of the State Standard of Uzbekistan, as well as drinking Hygienic requirements and quality control for drinking water fully comply with the requirements of the State Standard of Uzbekistan (UzDSt 0950:2011).

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Conclusion

The results of analysis of spring water samples were compared with the national standards of water quality of Uzbekistan. The results of the chemical analysis of spring water correspond to the requirements of the national standard of Uzbekistan (state standards for drinking and potable water).

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